

D8.1 – Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NoE	Network of Excellence

Executive Summary

The document presents a detailed communication and dissemination plan for the dAIEDGE project, which aims to establish a strong European ecosystem for distributed artificial intelligence at the edge. The plan outlines the objectives and strategies for disseminating the project results to the different target audiences. Starting from the identification of the target audience, the key messages, the communication schedule and the monitoring and evaluation measures.

The communication plan emphasises internal dissemination among the project partners using strategies to establish an effective and transparent collaboration within the project, involving all partners and stakeholders. In addition, it presents the actions to deepening the involvement of the scientific community, industry professionals, the general public and policy makers.

Based on the SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic, and Timely) methodology, the communication plan sets clear and robust objectives to build awareness, understanding and active engagement among various target groups. It ensures a thorough understanding of the project's objectives, activities and results, while fostering active engagement with key groups such as academics, practitioners and the general public.

The document also describes the measures for the expansion of the network through open calls, including the definition and management of these calls and the support programme for collaborative projects. It also details the creation of a strong visual identity and communication strategy, the project website, social media presence and the promotion of events to optimise stakeholder engagement and international recognition of the Network of Excellence.

Finally, the document presents a first version of the Exploitation plan, focusing on the expected exploitable results and the mechanisms that will be put in place to support the valorisation of the project's outcomes.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Project summary dAIEDGE presentation

The dAIEDGE Network of Excellence is a visionary initiative set to propel Europe to the forefront of edge AI technologies. In response to the evolving landscape of connected devices and the limitations of centralized AI models, the project seeks to establish a robust European ecosystem that harnesses the potential of distributed AI at the edge. By uniting research centres, industrial companies, policymakers, and standardization bodies, dAIEDGE aims to create a competitive edge AI environment, ensuring that Europe can effectively address societal challenges, enhance digital sovereignty, and lead in the development of emerging technologies.

The project's objectives, ranging from fostering innovation and collaborative research to creating virtual centres of excellence, underscore its commitment to advancing the field. Through annual roadmaps, lead-by-demonstration solutions, and a strong focus on privacy, security, and sustainability, dAIEDGE aims to not only strengthen Europe's position in edge AI but also contribute to the ethical development of digital technologies. By aligning with the principles of fundamental rights and environmental sustainability, the project sets out to ensure European autonomy in AI, reinforcing the region's values and leadership in the rapidly evolving landscape of artificial intelligence.

1.2. Scope and objectives of the deliverable

The dissemination and communication plan of the dAIEDGE project contains the guidelines that will mark the communication strategy throughout the development of the project. It is a fundamental document in which the dissemination activities and tools are described, detailing the type of key messages, objectives, graphic identity, upcoming activities, workshops, conferences, as well as the different communication channels.

Dissemination activities will help us to create a community of interest around the project objectives. The initial phase of the implementation of the communication strategy will focus on raising awareness of dAIEDGE and the ambitions it pursues in the technological field, as well as its impact on specific audiences at European level, but at the same time with a global reach.

The dissemination and communication strategy represents a continuous process from the beginning of the project and continues even after the end of the project as long as it is acted upon and there is a strong involvement of all actors involved. The dAIEDGE partners will play a key role in the development of the communication and dissemination strategy, as they will become brand ambassadors and the main spokespersons for the milestones, seminars, workshops, and achievement of the project's objectives.

1.3. Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable provides a comprehensive communication and dissemination plan for the dAIEDGE project. It outlines the objectives, strategies, and activities for disseminating project results to

various target audiences, including internal dissemination among project stakeholders. The deliverable is organized as follows:

Chapter 1 - "Introduction": A brief introduction outlines the objectives of the project and introduces the present deliverable in terms of dissemination.

Chapter 2 - "Project Communication Objectives and Strategy": This chapter describes the dissemination plan, analysing the target audiences and detailing how each will be addressed.

Chapter 3 - "Implementation Plan for C&D Activities": This chapter provides a detailed account of the implementation of the dissemination and communication strategy established by the project. It also outlines the tools that will be exploited to maximize the reach of results.

Chapter 4 - "C&D Activities Carried Out Up to M6": This chapter conducts an analysis of all performed C&D activities and their evaluation up to month 6.

Chapter 5 - "Extending the Network via Financial Support to Third Parties": This chapter highlights the open calls aiming to foster research exchange, solve industrial challenges, and showcase the capabilities of the Network of Excellence.

Chapter 6 - "DAIEDGE in the European Landscape": This chapter provides insights into European cybersecurity policies and the relevance of the project in the current landscape.

1.4. Relation to other project tasks

The communication actions are related in one way or another with the other dAIEDGE activities, although it is a horizontal relationship with each of the work packages of the project, seeking the greatest impact and the maximum scope of dissemination of the progress and activities developed, according to the target audiences. However, there are specific actions with relevant tasks that are detailed below:

dAIEDGE Communication and Dissemination plan Plan of the project communication and dissemination 8 IoT-DIH

T1.3 – European AI Lighthouse strategy Contribute to the strategy to establish the European Lighthouse and align with the objectives of the European Commission on the implementation and support to reach the critical mass of stakeholders.

T2.1 – Project management and coordination DFKI is task leader, IOT-DIH will contribute by attending all project meeting and reporting to the coordinator on all matters related to project progress. Other partners will contribute with their internal management of the project.

T8.2 - Expansion of the network through open calls Define and manage three open calls (OCs) as exchange programmes (1OC) and collaborative projects (2OCs).

2. Project communication objectives and strategy

2.1. Definitions

Before initiating the creation of a communication strategy for dAIEDGE, it is crucial to possess a clear comprehension of the fundamental definitions that will serve as the foundation and the necessary approach:

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): The scale and significance of the project's contribution is provided by Key Performance Indicators.

Key Expected Results (KER): Provide a clear and tangible way to assess progress, measure performance, and determine whether the project is meeting its intended outcomes.

Work Package (WP): A set of related tasks and activities grouped together to achieve specific project objectives, providing a structured framework for project management.

Milestone (MS): Significant points of achievement or completion marking key stages in the project timeline, crucial for assessing progress, adherence to timelines, and informing decision-making.

Communication: The intentional exchange of information, ideas, and messages among project stakeholders, utilizing various channels like project websites, social media, newsletters, and direct interactions.

Dissemination: A subset of communication that focuses on strategically spreading project-related content, outcomes, and calls to a broader audience, including the scientific community, industry professionals, the public, and policymakers.

Figure 1: Communication and Dissemination Framework in the Project.

2.2. SMART Communication Methodology

The SMART methodology is an excellent guide for success in planning and executing objectives. This approach, based on Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound goals, provides a robust framework to ensure that the proposed goals in a project are not only clear and quantifiable but also realistic and aligned with strategic purposes. Therefore, before communicating project

actions, it must be made clear that the SMART methodology will be employed. In this approach, the main key is consistency, taking into account the following factors:

- **Specific:** answering key specific questions (Who, What, Where, How, When, and Why?) to identify all unique communication objectives. Clear communication objectives will be established to determine methods, vehicles, goals, messages, benefits, stakeholders, and the project timeline.
- **Measurable:** establish criteria to evaluate the progress of project communication. Metrics are crucial in formulating a plan (e.g., social media analytics, surveys, sentiment analysis).
- **Achievable:** set realistic communication objectives and monitor the balance between quality and quantity.
- **Realistic and results-oriented:** establish criteria to determine if the project's goals and techniques are on track to achieve the intended objectives. Based on the response, assess the quality of communication. Identify potential improvement measures if project results are not as expected initially.
- **Time-conscious:** a good communication plan requires full compliance with the specified schedule and deadlines.

Figure 2. SMART methodology

2.3. Communication objectives and main strategy

The communication strategy for the dAIEDGE project is built upon a set of clear and robust objectives aimed at fostering awareness, understanding, and active engagement among diverse target groups. The primary objective is to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the project's goals, activities, and outcomes within the target audience. To achieve this, a user-friendly and informative project website will serve as the central online hub, providing detailed information on various aspects of the project. Additionally, social media platforms will be utilized to deliver regular updates, facilitate interactive communication, and engage with the audience. To complement online efforts, a range of communication materials, including technical and non-technical brochures, wallpapers, business cards, and posters, will be developed and distributed. Moreover,

the strategy emphasizes the promotion of open calls, highlighting opportunities for collaboration and community involvement.

Active engagement with target groups is another key objective, involving academics, professionals, and the general public in the project's activities. Social media platforms will play a crucial role, providing channels for direct interaction, announcements, and engagement initiatives. The strategy includes the organization of webinars, workshops, and seminars to facilitate meaningful dialogue and collaboration. Additionally, the distribution of informational materials to project partners, highlighting their roles and contributions, aims to strengthen relationships and foster a sense of shared ownership. Notably, the communication plan places a strong emphasis on promoting open calls as pivotal opportunities for collaboration, ensuring diverse and inclusive participation in the dAIEDGE project. Through these objectives and activities, the project aims to establish a dynamic and engaging communication strategy that aligns with its overarching goals and ensures a broad impact across its target audience.

2.4. Internal communication

The internal communication strategy is intricately designed to establish effective collaboration and transparency in the dAIEDGE project. The project ensures that project profiles are well-connected through methodologies like periodic follow-up meetings and access to updated planning documents. Utilizing diverse communication channels, including web platforms and newsletters, contributes to disseminating information efficiently. Work Package 8, specifically dedicated to Communication, plays a pivotal role in internal dissemination efforts. Responsibility assignment places IOT-DIH at the forefront of plan implementation, emphasizing their role in defining and executing communication strategies. The strategy's success hinges on creating a collaborative and transparent environment, ensuring stakeholders are consistently informed and engaged, thereby enhancing their ability to contribute meaningfully to the project's success.

2.5. Target audience

Another crucial aspect of developing a coherent and effective communication plan involves accurately identifying the target audience. It is self-evident that formulating a plan without a clear understanding of the intended recipients renders the effort futile. After establishing the goals, primary communication procedures, and defining the target audience, the next step is identifying their specific interest in the dAIEDGE project.

In the case of the dAIEDGE project, diverse solutions and technologies cater to distinct end users, including academics, technology industry professionals, various sector experts, the general public, and policymakers. These groups are categorized based on their specific interests and relevance to the project, ensuring that communication activities are tailored to address their unique needs. This targeted approach enhances the plan's efficiency and maximizes its impact across a diverse user base.

2.6. Target messages

Once the key objectives and target groups are established for the dAIEDGE project's communication strategy, the focus should shift to identifying the core messages that need to be conveyed. It is crucial to ensure clear and effective messaging, avoiding any confusion or miscommunication. Consider the following factors when identifying the appropriate target messages:

- Are the messages clear and concise for all stakeholders?
- Is the core message written in an active and positive tone?
- Does the message accurately represent the diverse activities of the dAIEDGE project?
- What are the expected outcomes of the primary message?

To ensure the target messages remain relevant, they will be regularly evaluated and updated within the dynamic landscape of edge AI. Consistent repetition is crucial to reinforce the key messages and ensure their adoption by the diverse target groups involved in the project. The messages will be designed to consider the characteristics and needs of these focus groups, ensuring a clear and understandable presentation.

2.7. Communication channels

Communication channels are the avenues through which information is exchanged, playing a crucial role in the success of the dAIEDGE project's outreach efforts. When deciding which channels to use, we must ask ourselves a few key questions:

- Who is our target audience?
- What message do we want to deliver?
- What are our objectives for message delivery?

Answering these questions helps identify the most effective communication channels to reach our target audience. Internal channels, such as team meetings and emails, play a key role in facilitating seamless communication within the project team. External channels, including newsletters, press releases, and social media platforms, enable engagement with a broader audience, from stakeholders to potential collaborators and the wider public.

Digital platforms like the official website and social media channels offer real-time updates and interactions, while traditional media, such as scientific journals, conferences, and commercial videos, extend the project's visibility. Direct engagement channels, exemplified by workshops and collaborative events, allow for hands-on demonstrations and training sessions.

This strategic approach ensures that messages are delivered efficiently, fostering understanding, collaboration, and awareness throughout the dAIEDGE initiative.

2.8. Communication timeline

Social media platforms, such as LinkedIn and Twitter, serve as valuable channels for fostering engagement and partnerships within the technical community. Regular posts on these platforms provide information about our technical meetings. Additionally, our blog, featured on the dAIEDGE

website, LinkedIn, and Twitter, delves into specific activities and noteworthy contributions from project partners during workshops.

dAIEDGE partners will attend conferences related to the project or addressing topics of interest to establish new partnerships with experts or similar projects. Additionally, a quarterly newsletter will be created, summarizing events and activities, seminars, workshops, and collaborations with other projects funded by the European Union.

Figure 3. Communication timeline

3. Implementation plan for C&D activities

3.1. Communication and Dissemination Activities for Achieving KPIs

Table 1 serves as a foundational guide for all C&D activities throughout the project's duration. It strategically details key activities and target values, emphasizing effective collaboration, and stakeholder engagement. In this classification, activities that involve sharing information with a broader audience or promoting awareness are categorized as "Dissemination," while activities that involve direct interaction or exchange of knowledge are categorized as "Communication."

Table 1: Communication and Dissemination Activities for Achieving KPIs

KPI Nr	KPI	Description	Target Value	Activity Needed
1	Number of scientific papers/articles related to edge AI submitted to journals, magazines, and conferences	Partners will contribute to scientific progress in edge AI.	>200 papers/articles	Dissemination
2	Number of academic exchanges and scientific visits	Facilitating academic exchanges to share knowledge and expertise.	>30 academic visits among NoE members	Communication
3	Number of patents filed by dAIEDGE partners	Recognizing and protecting innovative technologies developed in the project.	≥10 patents on relevant technologies	Dissemination
4	Successful demonstration of feasibility	Demonstrating efficiency in solving edge AI challenges through selected use cases.	≥3 use cases demonstrated and validated ≥20 demonstration areas proposed and supported via FSTP-funded collaborative projects	Dissemination
5	Number of common events co-organized with the EU AI Lighthouse	Collaborative events to advance the vision of the strategic agenda on AI research and promote Lighthouse activities.	≥20 common events with the EU AI Lighthouse	Communication

6	Stakeholder awareness in relevant sectors	Promoting project activities and business development to increase awareness among potential stakeholders.	≥2000 newsletter recipients ≥1000 posts in Social Networks	Dissemination
7	Number of centres of excellence joining dAIEDGE	dAIEDGE will start with a consortium of 35 partners, which will be extended thanks to our dissemination and incentive models.	≥150 centres of excellence in the dAIEDGE NoE across 30 countries	Dissemination
8	Number of studies/experiments conducted using the virtual research lab	Utilizing the virtual lab for joint experimentation within the NoE.	≥200 studies and experiments via the virtual research lab	Communication
9	Number of European assets available on the marketplace	Increasing the pool of reusable AI assets, applications, and solutions on the marketplace.	≥250,000 assets available in the marketplace	Dissemination
10	Number of collaborative European projects completed thanks to the dAIEDGE platform	Fostering collaborative projects using the dAIEDGE platform.	≥160 collaborative projects using the dAIEDGE platform	Communication
11	Number of projects and activities following dAIEDGE's recommendations and roadmaps	Adoption of project methodologies and roadmaps in subsequent EU or national projects.	≥10 EU or national projects referring to dAIEDGE methodology for edge AI technology development	Dissemination

12	Single users of applications using EU edge technology	Launching and promoting the exploitation of technologies developed in dAIEDGE for individual users.	≥150,000 users in Europe	Dissemination
13	Number of companies or industries using European edge AI solutions for worker empowerment	Encouraging companies to use European edge AI solutions to empower their workforce.	≥500 companies worldwide	Dissemination
14	Market share of European edge AI solutions	Establishing a significant market share for European edge AI solutions.	≥50% market share	Dissemination
15	Awareness of the general population about EU alternatives to edge AI technologies	Promoting dAIEDGE and "AI made in Europe" as a viable alternative to edge AI technologies.	≥50% of edge AI users aware of dAIEDGE solution	Dissemination
16	Choice of EU edge AI for privacy and ethical concerns	Encouraging users to choose EU alternatives for privacy and ethical reasons.	≥25% of edge AI users choose EU alternatives for privacy concerns	Dissemination

3.2. Audience

To comprehend the intricacies of the Edge AI project, it is crucial to identify the broad spectrum of stakeholders and audience integral to its success. The subsequent Table 2 meticulously examines the distinctive outcomes of these target audiences. This exploration lays the groundwork for shaping the project's C&D strategy, ensuring that engagement efforts are finely tuned to match the unique expectations and contributions of each audience

Table 2: Target audience groups for communication

Target Group	Outcomes
Academics	To achieve incremental knowledge transfer between different professionals by seeking to build a shared understanding of the technological and societal priorities for AI and systems in Europe across all industry sectors and to articulate the objectives and measures of success for a competitive European AI ecosystem.
Technology Industry Professionals	Build a shared understanding of the technological and societal priorities for AI and systems in Europe across industry sectors and articulate the objectives and success measures for a competitive European AI ecosystem, led by demonstration in the dAIEDGE Network of Excellence.
Professionals from Different Sectors	To increase the level of innovation and existing technology in production processes to achieve better results and efficiency
Society	Provide a new vision to society about the positive impact that the digital technologies related to AI, Edge computing and the intersection of both can have in current and future EU society.
Policy Makers	Generate innovative policies that benefit society as a whole, making them more efficient, optimal and leading to a better development of the regions. These new policies will be supported by the advances that are being developed and achieved in the dAIEDGE Network of Excellence.

3.2.1. Target groups enrolment in communication Activities

At the core of the dAIEDGE project's success lies an effective communication strategy that actively involves various target groups. Table 3 meticulously outlines the planned enrolment of these groups in specific communication activities.

Table 3: Target groups enrolment in communication activities

Target Group	Communication Activities	Interest in the Project
Academics	Web, social media, scientific workshops, seminars, hackathons, publications, conferences, journals	<p>Emphasize the opportunity to contribute to the development of edge AI, aligning with European values.</p> <p>Highlight the role of academic research personnel in shaping the future of AI at the edge.</p>
Technology Industry Professionals	Web, social media, scientific workshops, workshops, seminars, participation in specialized magazines, events	Communicate the availability of resources, knowledge, and open platforms for industry professionals.
Professionals from Different Sectors	Web, social media, workshops, seminars, events	<p>Showcase the relevance of edge AI across sectors like robotics, health, agriculture, and manufacturing.</p> <p>Highlight the potential impact on specific industries through collaboration.</p>
Society	Web, social media, hackathons, press releases, blog entries, social networks, promotional videos, activities, newsletter	<p>Communicate the benefits of edge AI technologies for workers and citizens.</p> <p>Emphasize the commitment to data security, privacy, and European values in AI development.</p>
Policy Makers	Web, social media, direct contact through partners, dedicated communications such as research agendas and white papers	<p>Emphasize compliance with European values in edge AI development.</p> <p>Communicate the project's alignment with public agencies, observatories, think-tanks, and regulators.</p>

3.3. Channels

3.3.1. Project Website

The dAIEDGE project website, accessible at - daiedge.eu and serves as the main communication tool and first point of contact for all official project news and information. It is an essential tool to ensure transparency and to keep stakeholders informed about the progress of the project.

The website and its content are regularly updated according to the progress of the project. The content is maintained by IoT DIH. The content is created jointly with the help of partners to ensure its accuracy and timeliness.

Regular updates of the website will include information on the project's objectives, progress and milestones achieved. In addition, it will also provide detailed information on the project structure, partners and work packages involved.

Overall, the dAIEDGE project website is an effective channel for communicating with stakeholders and ensuring that they are well informed about project developments.

3.3.2. Social Media

The communication strategy of dAIEDGE will follow the objectives of the project, in order to create a community interested in learning about the advances and opportunities offered by Artificial Intelligence and other technologies. To this end, several dissemination channels will be created (web and social networks), through which stakeholders will be kept informed of events, activities and advances in the project.

To achieve these objectives, the target audience will be established, and from there a plan will be designed for periodic publications adapted to the target, in which the interactions of users will be contemplated and analysed in order to verify the effectiveness of the message.

Social networks will help us to capture the attention of researchers, companies and institutions interested in AI advances. In this sense, we will create valuable content publications contributed by the project partners. In addition, a publication calendar will be set up to keep track of the progress and activities of the dAIEDGE project.

In order to increase interactions and reach out to other profiles, the social networks of the partners will be linked so that they can share the content more easily. In addition to accompanying the posts with the following tags (#dAIEDGE #dAIEDGEProject #NOE) and adding other hashtags related to the publication.

The IoT DIH, in collaboration with its partners, will be responsible for generating and maintaining the channels created, they are:

LinkedIn - <https://www.linkedin.com/company/daiedge/>

Twitter - <https://twitter.com/dAIEDGE>

3.3.3. Social media-Partners and Participants

One of the communication objectives of dAIEDGE is to create a community interested in learning about the progress of the project and that in turn can echo the importance of artificial intelligence. To do this, we will count on the collaboration of all partners through the creation of content that will help us to glimpse the progress in their work packages.

In this sense, we invite all partners to collaborate and become spokespersons for this initiative, from publications in their social networks, comments, likes, and other actions that allow us to reach the widest possible audience.

3.3.4. Newsletters

As part of dAIEDGE's dissemination actions, a quarterly newsletter will be sent out summarising the project's activities, progress and milestones.

The newsletter will allow a direct connection with the audience while generating traffic to the dAIEDGE website and social networks, which contributes to brand positioning.

The image shows a screenshot of a newsletter subscription form on the dAIEDGE website. At the top, the dAIEDGE logo is displayed, consisting of a stylized blue 'd' and 'AI' followed by 'EDGE' in a bold, sans-serif font. Below the logo, the text 'Network of Excellence (NoE)' is centered. The form itself is a white box with a light gray border. It contains the following elements: a short introductory paragraph about the newsletter; a red asterisk indicating required fields; input fields for 'E-mail address*', 'Name*', and 'Surname'; a dropdown menu for 'Affiliation*' with 'Citizen' selected; a section for 'Marketing Permissions' with a sub-instruction 'Please select how you would like to receive our news from the options below.' and a checkbox for 'Email'.

Figure 4. dAIEDGE's newsletter subscription on the website

3.3.5. Communication material

We have created communication material for fairs, meetings and events. Figures 5 and 6 present the dAIEDGE flyer and the dAIEDGE roll-up models. This material can be printed and is available on the website.

Figure 5. DAIEDGE's flyer

Figure 6. DAIEDGE's Roll-up

3.3.6. Target groups

In the following tables, we list the identified target groups, the corresponding key message, tools and channels, as well as the expected outcomes of the communication to these target groups.

Target group A	Academics – Public, cultural or educational entities, universities, laboratories and research centres in specific areas of knowledge associated with aspects of AI at the Edge, that can leverage or contribute knowledge, or benefit from knowledge extracted from the development of the project.
Key Message	Participation in the dAI ^{EDGE} Network of Excellence. Knowledge and capacity building through participation in a network of excellence that seeks to strengthen and support the development of the dynamic European AI ecosystem at the edge under the umbrella of the European AI Lighthouse.
Tools & Channels	Web, social media, scientific workshops, seminars, hackathons, publications.
Outcomes	To achieve incremental knowledge transfer between different professionals by seeking to build a shared understanding of the technological and societal priorities for AI and systems in Europe across all industry sectors and to articulate the objectives and measures of success for a competitive European AI ecosystem.

Target group B	Technology industry professionals – Professionals in the field of AI and edge technology who can benefit from the implementation of the obtained knowledge or who could work with it.
Key Message	Participate in a network of technological excellence where knowledge can be shared and increased for greater efficiency and innovation, to sustain advanced research and innovation in distributed AI at the edge as an essential, enabling, and emerging digital technology across a wide range of industry sectors.
Tools & Channels	Web, social media, academic dissemination, scientific workshops, workshops, seminars.

Target group C	Professionals from different sectors – Professionals in different business sectors that can improve their processes and thus benefit from the implementation of the knowledge developed.
Key Message	Participation in a network of technological excellence that can, through collaboration, contribute development and expertise via the advancement of cutting-edge AI research and innovation.
Tools & Channels	Web, social media, workshops, seminars

Outcomes	To increase the level of innovation and existing technology in production processes to achieve better results and efficiency
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Target group D	Society – The entirety of today's society that may benefit from the project's progress, both directly and indirectly.
Key Message	Show the results, progress and knowledge that the project is achieving and that can be highly interesting for citizens and society as a whole, creating a community and expanding the network.
Tools & Channels	Web, social media, hackathons
Outcomes	Provide a new vision to society about the positive impact that the digital technologies related to AI, Edge computing and the intersection of both can have in current and future EU society.

Target group E	Policy makers – Authorities responsible for deciding on the policies of an area or region or in charge of establishing new policies (EU, national, and regional-level).
Key Message	See the current reality of the advancement of technologies such as AI and how they can positively influence society, constituting a breakthrough that could enable future EU leadership in Edge AI at all levels.
Tools & Channels	Web, social media, direct contact through partners in the consortium, dedicated communications such as research agendas and white papers
Outcomes	Generate innovative policies that benefit society as a whole, making them more efficient, optimal and leading to a better development of the regions. These new policies will be supported by the advances that are being developed and achieved in the dAI ^{EDGE} Network of Excellence.

3.3.7. Communication actions with other projects

Ensuring robust communication with other projects is paramount to disseminating its unique concept among partners in diverse consortia, featuring members from various countries. Additionally, fostering the exchange of scientific results between projects serves as a catalyst for effective problem-solving and risk mitigation by facilitating the sharing of experiences and corrective measures in analogous scenarios.

Embracing open-mindedness, the dAIEDGE consortium actively seeks collaboration with other projects in the expansive field of network AI. Projects related to dAIEDGE can be classified into three categories: Starting, In Progress, and Finished.

Consequently, the consortium establishes vital connections and communication channels with parallel initiatives within the Horizon CL4 European Network of AI Excellence Centres: expanding the European AI lighthouse (RIA).

The project partners have been and are currently involved in related EU-funded and national R&D projects in various frameworks. Related projects are listed in Table 4.

Table 4: Related projects

PROJECT	STATUS	PARTNER	RESULT TO BE USED
Eyes of Things (Grant n. 643924)	Finished	UCLM,DFKI, THALES	Eyes of Things developed a ground breaking small artificial vision system for edge applications, including optimized deep learning inference on a power budget. An evolved version is the CogniSat platform by partner Ubotica, to be used in tests in dAI ^{EDGE} .
Platform for Open Development of Systems of Artificial Intelligence - Bonseyes (Grant n. 732204)	Finished	BCA,HES-SO, BTH, UEDIN	We will expand and integrate the Bonseyes AI Marketplace platform with AIoD to enhance its features and facilitate deployment and use of dAI ^{EDGE} AI assets.
HUMANE-AI (ICT-48)	In progress	DFKI, CNRS, ETHZ, FHG, INRIA, SU, THALES	Coordination of the HUMANE-AI and dAIEDGE NoE and alignment towards implementation of the EU AI Lighthouse vision
VISION CSA (ICT-48)		DFKI, INRIA, THALES	Expertise in synergy and interaction between networks of excellence
TAILOR (ICT-48)	In progress	DFKI, INRIA, CNRS, CEA, FHG	Roadmaps on Trustworthy AI - Integrating Reasoning, Learning and Optimization
From Copernicus Big Data to Extreme Earth Analytics - ExtremeEarth (Grant n. 825258)	Finished	DLR	Expertise in data and big data, AI expertise for remote observation
Edge AI – HORIZON KDT JU	In progress	SINTEF, IMEC, ST	Building core edge AI hardware infrastructure

REBECCA-HORIZON KDT-JU-2021-2-RIA Reconfigurable Heterogeneous Highly Parallel Processing Platform for safe and secure AI	Starting	CSEM, BCA, IMEC,FORT H, UCLM	Developing a purely European complete Hardware and Software stack around a RISC-V CPU, which will provide significantly higher levels of performance, energy/power efficiency, safety and security.
STAIRWAI AI-ICT-49 matchmaking for SMEs	Finished	BCA, THALES, FBA	Horizontal and vertical matchmaking engine to be integrated in AIoD platform
BONSAPPS –ICT-49 AI-as-a-Service for the Deep Edge	Finished	ST-I, BCA, HES-SO, BTH, FBA	Services layer in Bonseyes AI Marketplace, interoperable with AIoD platform, for experimentation /model optimisation /deployment of edge devices /security & licensing
AI4EUROPE CSA - HORIZON-CL4-2021- HUMAN-01	In progress	FHG, DFKI	Developing an open EU platform for AI research
Prep-AI-DIGITAL- 2021-CLOUD-AI-01- PREP-AI	Finished	FBA	Definition of requirements for the new phase of the AIoD under DIGITAL
ANDANTE ECSEL-JU	In progress	CSEM, THALES, IMEC, ST	HW/SW platforms based on efficient Neuromorphic, artificial and spiking neural networks, solutions

3.4. Audience and channel matching

The target groups have been identified, as well as the communication strategies recommended for each of them. However, it is worth noting that despite the established links between the channels, as presented in the table, these channels will not be strictly and exclusively linked throughout the entire project.

Initially, the implementation of these actions is considered to be the most effective means of disseminating the objectives of dAIEDGE among the target audiences. However, this message will be periodically updated throughout the project as part of the continuous development process of the communication plan, in accordance with the new needs identified in each of the audiences.

Engaging with academics involves a multifaceted approach, utilizing web platforms, social media, scientific workshops, seminars, hackathons, and publications. An excellent example is the pioneering work of Eyes of Things, which has developed an artificial vision system for edge

applications, including the innovative CogniSat platform in collaboration with Ubotica, that will be used for testing in dAIEDGE.

Similarly, reaching out to technology industry professionals necessitates a comprehensive strategy involving web platforms, social media, academic dissemination, and participation in relevant events. This could entail publishing in specialized journals, attending gatherings such as Startup Olé and Digital Enterprise Show, and consistently sharing updates through newsletters.

Engagement with professionals from different sectors requires a diverse range of activities, including web platforms, social media, workshops, and seminars. Active participation in events such as Startup Olé and Digital Enterprise Show, along with the regular distribution of newsletters, will foster ongoing connections and collaboration.

Connecting with the society at large requires an array of communication methods, which span web platforms, social media, and hackathons. From press releases and blog entries to interesting videos and participation in events like European Researcher nights.

Lastly, policy makers can be effectively engaged by leveraging web platforms and social media, as well as through direct contact via consortium partners. Through initiatives such as research agendas, white papers, descriptive reports, and strategic meetings, the project seeks to secure support and advocacy for its continuation and broader impact.

4. Communication and Dissemination activities carried out up to M6

Since the launch of the dAIEDGE, communication and dissemination activities have been carried out through different channels, with the aim of publicising the progress of the project, from the launch of the corporate image, website, workshops, presence in forums, conferences, as well as the actions that will be carried out in the coming months.

Active collaboration with partners and stakeholders has been key to achieving the objectives so far. The project has facilitated the exchange of materials of interest and alliances with similar initiatives or networks. Each of the actions implemented has been key to reach the target audience, to successfully disseminate the milestones achieved and to promote the dAIEDGE project.

4.1. Branding

For an initiative like dAIEDGE, branding is the tangible manifestation of its purpose and contribution to knowledge. Strong and distinctive branding not only brings instant recognition, but also builds a coherent narrative around the project. To keep the brand in sync, brand guidelines were established along the lines of each of the creative and communication materials. As a result, the dAIEDGE brand has started to gain traction on social media with an excellent acceptance by the target audience, which has increased the visibility and credibility of the project.

4.1.1. Branding strategy

Strong and distinctive branding not only brings instant recognition, but also builds a coherent narrative around the project. Therefore, after analysing dAIEDGE's objectives, a brand strategy was designed that encompasses the values, goals and desired scope of the project. Well-crafted

branding increases the visibility of the project, which attracts potential collaborators, media and above all, the target audience for which dAIEDGE has been launched.

Figure 7. Principal channels

Advertising Material (Brochure, One Pager, Flyer):

For the broader dissemination of the project, a brochure was created outlining the main objectives and ambitions of dAIEDGE. The flyer includes detailed yet understandable information to reach a wide audience. Corporate identity played a crucial role in creating promotional material consistent with the project.

Contact information was provided along with a clear call to action for interested individuals to access all information through a QR code redirecting them to the website. Headlines, bullet points, and short paragraphs were also utilized to make the brochure easy to read and comprehend.

4.1.2. Graphic identity

The logo depicts a beam of light which represents the intersection of artificial intelligence and a high-speed computer network. The circular shape at the top is inspired by the connection points that allude to both technology and connectivity, as well as the union of the consortium that forms the European Network of AI Centres of Excellence.

The colour palette is composed of blue tones, representing technology and artificial intelligence. We used a straight, linear and geometric typography to represent a fast and agile technological network. [View brand book](#)

Figure 8. Graphic identity

dAIEDGE BRAND IDENTITY

5. OUR COLOUR PALETTE

The chromatic range used for dAIEDGE is made up of blue tones, these tones represent technology and Artificial Intelligence.

Color Code	CMYK	RGB
#1947ed	C:88% M:67% Y:0% K:0%	R:25 G:71 B:237
#121a37	C:100% M:92% Y:44% K:49%	R:18 G:26 B:55
#4a3179	C:82% M:88% Y:6% K:1%	R:74 G:49 B:121

Figure 9. Colour Palette

4.2. Project website

The dAIEDGE project website, available at <https://daiedge.eu/>, The platform serves as the central hub for communication, acting as the primary point of contact for all official project updates and information. Its pivotal role lies in fostering transparency and ensuring stakeholders are consistently informed about the project's progress.

Figure 10. Project Website

4.2.1. Website structure

The dAIEDGE website, described from a technical point of view, is developed in Drupal 9. The following programming languages have been used for its construction: PHP-TWIG, to connect to the database and manage the contents, HTML to build the structure and CSS to layout the styles. The visual aspect is structured as follows:

Figure 11. Website structure

4.3. Social media presence

Leveraging social networks proves to be a crucial asset in promoting our project. By establishing a strong presence on major platforms, we not only enable interaction and the dissemination of our project's ideas and goals but also create a prime avenue for connecting with our target audience.

The realm of social media offers an indispensable resource for gathering information and receiving valuable feedback on our project. Here, we can actively engage in market research, conduct surveys, and analyse data to gain profound insights into the needs and preferences of our audience. Furthermore, it serves as an optimal channel for receiving direct feedback, empowering us to refine and customize the project to precisely meet the specific needs of our audience.

4.3.1. X (Twitter)

X, a dynamic and widely-used social media platform, is a key component of the dAIEDGE project's dissemination strategy. With its millions of active users globally, Twitter offers a real-time avenue to share project updates, achievements, and relevant content. By utilizing hashtags and engaging with the edge AI community, we can effectively amplify the project's messages, attract the attention of potential collaborators, and foster meaningful interactions. The platform's brevity and immediacy make it an ideal space for concise updates, creating a vibrant online presence and promoting engagement among academics, industry professionals, and the wider target audience.

Figure 12. C&D activities on Twitter

4.3.2. LinkedIn

LinkedIn, a powerful professional networking platform with millions of active users worldwide, is a strategic choice for the dAIEDGE project's dissemination strategy. By leveraging LinkedIn, a broad and diverse audience composed of academics, industry professionals, stakeholders, and individuals interested in the advancements of edge AI can be effectively reached. Through regular updates, engaging content, and participation in relevant groups and discussions, the project aims to capture the attention of the target audience and establish valuable connections within the professional community.

Figure 13. C&D activities on LinkedIn

4.3.3. Social media update timeline

In the initial phase, we will commence our communication strategy with a project announcement and introduction, opting for a modest posting frequency of 3 times per week on social media during the first months. As the project gains momentum and tangible results surface, we plan to enhance

our engagement by increasing social media posts per week in the following months. Additionally, we aim to introduce blog posts, articles, and online events to supplement our communication efforts. Throughout the entire timeline, our strategy will remain adaptive, scaling the frequency of communication as the project progresses and audience interest grows.

4.4. Monitoring, evaluation, and impact assessment

4.4.1. Project C&D monitoring tool

The project proposal does not mention a specific tool to monitor project communication and dissemination activities. The project will use various communication channels such as social media, press releases, newsletters, factsheets, brochures, flyers, posters, roll-ups, and public engagement events to disseminate project results and connect with target audiences.

Research papers will be published on the dAIEDGE website in a section dedicated to scientific publications, in addition to participating in conferences and workshops. Project coordination is outlined in WP1, where an effective structure for project management, planning, and monitoring activities will be established. Progress reports, milestone reports, budget summaries, reviews, and day-to-day administrative and management functions will be periodically carried out.

For monitoring communication and dissemination of our online presence, we have used the following measurement tools.

4.4.2. Google Analytic

Google Analytics is the essential strategic ally for any project aiming for excellence in the digital realm. With the implementation of this tool, we can measure performance, from tracking conversions to assessing user behaviour. Each click, each interaction, becomes valuable data that informs decision-making to evaluate the efficiency of our online presence.

Figure 14. Google Analytics, last quarter report

4.4.3. LinkedIn Analytics

Metrics are a key factor in evaluating the role we are playing in different communication channels. In the case of LinkedIn, we use the metrics provided by the platform, which are based on the number of followers, impressions, likes, and, above all, the level of engagement of our project with the target audience. This data will also help us make decisions in future outreach actions.

Figure 15. LinkedIn Analytics

4.4.4. X (Twitter) Analytics

To assess the actions being carried out on X, we use the X Analytics tool itself. From there, we obtain valuable information about the performance of posts, audience engagement, and follower growth on the dAIEDGE profile. The ability to analyse real-time data allows for agile decision-making and continuous optimization of the strategy on this platform.

Figure 16. X Analytics

5. Extending the Network via Financial Support to Third Parties

In pursuit of fostering a dynamic environment for research, collaboration, and industrial innovation, dAIEDGE is committed to a strategic plan spanning 36 months. This commitment is outlined through carefully curated Open Calls at the core of the initiative, comprising targeted programs to enhance

mobility, facilitate research exchange, and address industrial challenges through collaborative projects. This roadmap signifies our dedication to engaging with third-party projects, welcoming diverse talents and perspectives into the dAIEDGE network.

Our goal is to engage 30 third-party projects to foster mobility, research exchange, and perform industrial research. This will be achieved through the publication of three open calls, each with specific tracks and objectives:

1. Exchange Programmes Open Call: Selecting up to 10 beneficiaries for research visits to hosting organizations within dAIEDGE members.
2. Open Call for Collaborative Projects: Selecting up to 20 third-party Collaborative Projects aimed at using the dAIEDGE Virtual Lab to solve specific industrial challenges defined by the project.

5.1. Selection Procedures and Evaluation Criteria

For each Open Call, a meticulous procedure will be followed. This includes the establishment of a selection committee, the launch of a rigorous selection process, evaluation of candidates, and continuous monitoring of project execution. Specific challenges will be articulated before each call to guide proposal submissions.

5.2. Supporting Beneficiaries and Network Expansion

Upon selection, beneficiaries will sign Sub Grants Agreements, and the consortium will provide ongoing support. This assistance aims to help them leverage the knowledge and assets within dAIEDGE, ultimately leading to the incorporation of additional researchers and innovative companies into the network.

5.3. Promotion and Information Dissemination

To ensure widespread participation, IOT-DIH will play a pivotal role in promoting and disseminating information about the three Open Calls. These efforts will contribute to attracting a diverse pool of participants and fostering a collaborative environment.

Recognizing Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) as pioneers in adopting emerging technology trends, they are identified as ideal target partners for dAIEDGE.

5.3.1. Timeline for Open Calls

For a detailed breakdown and specific information regarding the timeline for open calls, please refer to Annex A, which provides a comprehensive overview, including details pertaining to each stage of the open call process.

Note that we propose a slightly modified timeline for the Open Call (OC) process for following reason:

When OCs were planned in the proposal phase of the project, the actual starting date of the project was unknown. For this reason, when planning the OCs dates, the necessary progress time was correct, but it could not be known in which time of the year the OC will be opened. In addition, in

proposal preparation a duration of 3 months for the OCs was planned, whereas only 2 months mandatory as per EC rules.

The 1st OC (Exchange Programs) was planned to start on month 11 of the project, that would mean July '24. As it is proven in our experience in OCs, summer months are not good to ensure applicants for the OC, especially in this one that is targeted for researchers, so we propose to delay the opening of the OC to the end of August and keep it open until the end of October. This will not mean any other delays in the project, as the exchange dates should be negotiated among beneficiaries and hosting organizations.

For the 2nd and 3rd Open Calls (Collaborative projects) we propose to keep them open for two months, which means a reduction of one month compared to the plan. This will ensure that the Support Programs organization can continue as planned.

6. dAIEDGE in the European landscape - a policy context

The project aims to address specific needs and expected results related to the sovereignty of Europe in edge AI technologies, gathering forces in research and industry in edge AI, resource accessibility, and sustainability. It also aligns with the European AI Lighthouse initiative, which seeks to accelerate research and capability development efforts in edge AI technology and security, and increase investments in cutting-edge research, innovation, and digitalization.

The project's implementation plan for demonstration activities includes several key components. It aims to provide feedback to policy measures by formulating recommendations, roadmaps, and a strategic research agenda for Europe in the domain of edge AI. This involves participating in the foundation of a European vision of AI in cooperation with EU policymakers and serving as a reference body of experts for creating, monitoring, reviewing, and suggesting modifications of policies about AI in Europe. Additionally, the project focuses on impact measures such as visual identity, website, social media identity, press releases, liaison with stakeholders, public engagement, newsletters, market-specific material, and co-hosting events with similar EU or national projects. Furthermore, the project aims to nurture relations with SME support networks and AI associations, offer open-source solutions, and engage existing customer relationships in the vertical use cases.

In the European landscape, the dAIEDGE project is strategically positioned to contribute to the establishment of the European AI Lighthouse, strengthen the edge AI ecosystem, and support the development of advanced research and innovation in distributed AI at the edge. It aims to reinforce value chains and networks, accelerate digital and green transitions, and enhance Europe's existing assets. The project also seeks to foster synergies with other European AI initiatives and partnerships, advance Europe's innovation and technological base, and develop a comprehensive policy and governance approach to AI for the EU to become a global leader in innovation in the data economy and its applications.

In addition, the activities of the NoE will produce management data like membership lists, lists of participants in events, survey scores for events. These data are not considered research data and

are processed in compliance with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) The project coordinator shall ensure that any person engaged in the project complies with the applicable laws or regulations relating to the collection, processing and protection of personal data in the applicable jurisdiction.

7. Exploitation plan

The dAIEDGE project will define and implement an exploitation plan for the activities developed during the life of the project, ensuring its sustainability. Although the project is a Network of Excellence and not an innovation action, it will define paths to exploitation and sustainability, in coordination with other relevant EU projects. BCA will define the exploitation plan and follow the exploitation implementation together with IOT-DIH in coordination with the other partners.

7.1. Key Expected Results (KERs)

The Key Expected Results identified for Exploitation for dAIEDGE are as follows:

- KER2: Virtual research lab for edge AI – Laboratory for conducting common research and experiments across the domains of edge AI and across communities, facilitated by dedicated tools and services
- KER4: Benchmarks and benchmarking tools – Standardized, easily accessible, and usable benchmarks for edge AI capacity, facilitated by benchmarking tools and services
- KER6: Collaborative projects – Support for research and development projects on edge AI for industrial partners (in particular SMEs) and consortia of multiple partners (industry/academia)
- KER7: Three validation use cases of the dAIEDGE technical advances following our lead-by-demonstration principle
- KER8: Marketplace and business incubator – Exploitation strategy based on the development of a marketplace for edge AI solutions and creation of an incubator for facilitating the exploitation and market-readiness of the European edge technologies

7.2. Delivery mechanisms for Exploitation

The KERs of the project that will act as conduct for exploitation of the results of the project are the Virtual Lab, the Business Incubator and the Marketplace in terms of delivery mechanisms. In terms of content, the project will also identify assets and services that could be exploited, either by individual partners, or jointly.

Figure 17: The three stages of value creation in dAIEDGE

7.2.1. Virtual Lab

The dAIEDGE's virtual lab developed in WP4 will be a federation of lab resources and initially based on the contributed assets by the partners. It will allow for the collaborative sharing of dedicated Edge AI resources for research and experimentation and provide the core layer for the dAIEDGE NoE to provide a venue for technical and research collaborations towards new assets and services that may be exploited subsequently in a new innovation cycle. The resource management on the VLab will be based on formal open APIs for interconnecting, aggregating, and enabling remote access to research infrastructures and other resources/assets.

The Virtual Lab will become the venue for projects to develop their experimentation phase before they can be exploited and / or commercialised in a subsequent phase in the innovation cycle.

Why a distributed research VLab ? The benefits for an effective innovation cycle based on such venue are many:

- Provide a decentralized network of resources that researchers/developers can tap into, offering improved resource availability
- Centralised cloud model is constrained by supply of resources, not demand
- Incentivize users to direct or deploy hardware to offer fungible, digital resources
- Generate network effects, easier to scale,
- No massive upfront investment needed, adding or adjusting virtual resources
- Improve access, and reduce costs with more flexibility

7.2.2. Marketplace

Connecting and channelling the outcomes of the dAIEDGE project and the related networks with the AI-on demand platform and the Bonseyes AI Marketplace through integration will allow to bridge the gap between research, innovation and industry by making available collaborative tools and services for the development and deployment of re-usable AI assets and applications on embedded and edge devices, avoiding the route of large integrated solutions and platform mainly from US technology firms. The dAIEDGE project will specifically allow the Bonseyes AI marketplace to expand its present model of a distributed automated procurement process by including more ecosystem participants and working towards developing a fully automated supply chain for the

building and delivery of AI solutions ‘at the edge’. It will add to both the supply side (with algorithms, models, training, data scientists, software platforms) as well as the offer side (making available AI artefacts, AI applications, various embedded systems platforms) that can meet and transact in a secure and scalable way on a secure platform with microservices.

Similarly, the dAIEDGE results and innovations will be connected to the newly developed European AI-on-Demand for the collaborative sharing of AI assets and services, in two directions:

- Interoperability with **AI4Europe** research platform
- Interoperability with the future **Deploy AI** industry marketplace for SMEs and Innovators

Finally the task will examine and evaluate how to develop interoperability with the TEF platforms specifically dedicated to Edge AI resources to expand the reach of the Vlab.

7.2.3. Business Incubator:

Alongside the Virtual lab and the Marketplace, the third leg of the value chain for dAIEDGE community is the Business Incubator, discussed in WP7. It will be addressing the exploitation and sustainability aspects of the dAIEDGE activities, providing a forum for the stakeholders from the research, industry and investment community to discuss how to scale the Edge AI initiatives and results into sustainable results, in the form of spin-offs, start-ups, or new projects internalised in the AI enterprise sector (software and hardware).

The virtual business incubator will help showcase and incubate impactful success stories that will generate traction with the European AI ecosystem. It will boost the network attractiveness for SMEs by bringing in investors financing, grow network effects with the inclusion / invitation of specialized business partners such as business experts, business networks, start-ups, SMEs, companies as well as some public administrations and investors and venture capital firms for multiple market verticals to ensure business adoption and long-term sustainability by generating a positive feedback loop between network supply and demand. This task will help catalyse development through a platform that provides opportunity to European academic and industrial AI laboratories to exploit the outputs of the project. The virtual incubator will be accessible through the project website. The aim of the task will be to promote the project results and establish a strong usability beyond the project lifecycle. For this task to be successful, a comprehensive analysis will be conducted to identify potential exploitation opportunities, having self-sustainability of the project in mind.

The combination of the Virtual lab, the Marketplace and the Incubator activities will help activate a Flywheel for the network effects in dAIEDGE as outline in the WP4 plans, in particular with respect to the virtual lab.

Figure 18: Flywheel for VLab and dAIEDGE ecosystem

7.3. Exploitation strategy

7.3.1. Main content for exploitation

Key content to be considered for dissemination and possible exploitation are the following Key Expected results from the project:

- KER4: Benchmarks and benchmarking tools – Standardized, easily accessible, and usable benchmarks for edge AI capacity, facilitated by benchmarking tools and services
- KER6: Collaborative projects – Support for research and development projects on edge AI for industrial partners (in particular SMEs) and consortia of multiple partners (industry/academia)
- KER7: Three validation use cases of the dAIEDGE technical advances following our lead-by-demonstration principle

7.3.2. High-level requirements

The high-level requirements to facilitate exploitation of AI assets and services within dAIEDGE are the following:

- A set of fully developed and RE-USABLE AI assets and AI services
- Core processes and tools to experiment, build and deploy the resulting AI solutions – from Research to Industr
- A Virtual Lab / Playground for experimentation (research focused)
- A secure, trustworthy Marketplace with IPR enforcement for scalable & meaningful enterprise adoption (industry focused)
- An enterprise-friendly User Interface and 'Studio Services' (business, legal, funding, etc.) to provide support to SMEs
- A sustainable governance & business model that allows trustworthy growth and adoption

7.3.3. Activities planned with respect to exploitation

The Virtual Incubator will be set up encourage funding deep tech and Edge AI initiatives and facilitate go-to-market with studio services. An initial list will be drawn of potential participants and stakeholders into these activities. The activities under this task are: 1) aligned with other WPs, define the value proposition and core objectives; 2) focusing on engagement of early adopters; 3) aiming to expand the network; 4) during project's scale-up phase, potential investors will be engaged, and nurtured through introductions and innovation showcases/network event.

Objectives for Virtual Incubator

- Build a community / network of AI Talents, SMEs, FSTP participants and Investors around the project activities and results in the field of Edge AI
- The virtual incubator will promote the Project results, share success stories and establish a strong usability beyond the project lifecycle
- New projects & products relevant to the Network to be showcased to SMEs and Investors
- Proactively spotting innovations that may have a potential for exploitation
- Provide active venture building support for SMEs -> giving the SMEs a helping hand to reach investment readiness

Key activities

- Organise Virtual business incubator (in coordination with AI on demand platform) [M24]
- Draw list of targeted participants outside dAIEDGE and invite them (AI Talents/SMEs/VCS)
- Get the community / network participants to win to subscribe / sign up to the platform and/or to the VCoE/VLab
- Organise a Match-making event for business incubation [M34]
- Organise Workshop on industrial and investments priorities [M34]

The consortium will leverage on existing tools for accessing them and more than 250 AI talents, AI experts (developers, researchers, data scientists) and SMEs willing to consume AI services collected from two contributing projects ICT 49 (Bonsapps, StairwAI) and 400 hundred from Robotics4EU to this aim. A number of the ICT 49 projects, have developed for the AIoD a large initial pool of validated AI experts, AI talents (developers, data scientists, researchers) and SMEs willing to consume AI services. They will be invited to participate in the dAIEDGE activities with respect to dissemination and exploitation.

7.4. Knowledge Management Strategy and IPR

For the success of dAIEDGE it is essential that all project partners agree on explicit rules concerning IP ownership, access rights to any Background and Foreground IP for the execution of the project and the protection of intellectual property rights (IPRs) and confidential information to avoid conflict of interest.

- Those rules are specified in the Consortium Agreement (CA) in which will be established clearly and in detail the conditions under which either the consortium as a whole or its individual partners will share the rights of exploitation results after the completion of the project.
- The intellectual property in the project will be monitored and managed from the beginning by collecting the foreseen license of components and assets to be generated. This practice will ensure that the results will be perfectly exploitable at the optimal case, as there will not be conflicts of interest by any party and between components.

8. Conclusions

This Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan for the dAIEDGE Project is designed as a dynamic framework that will continuously update and adapt to the evolving needs of the project to effectively reach its goals. Recognizing the dynamic nature of the technological landscape and the diverse range of stakeholders involved, the plan emphasizes a commitment to ongoing assessment and refinement. For the communication and dissemination part, regular reviews of communication strategies, channels, and messaging will be undertaken to ensure relevance and resonance with the target audience. The plan's agility in responding to emerging trends and technologies will be a cornerstone, allowing it to remain adaptive and aligned with the project's trajectory. As the project progresses, feedback mechanisms and performance metrics will be leveraged to identify areas for improvement, ensuring that the communication efforts remain robust, impactful, and reflective of the project's achievements. This iterative approach will allow us to stay at the forefront of effective communication practices, ultimately contributing to the success and broader impact of the dAIEDGE Project. For the exploitation part, exploitable assets will become more identifiable and concrete as the project progresses. Therefore, the exploitation strategy will be refined at month M18 and M30.

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11. ANNEX A

The following chart presents the activities related to the Open Calls with the updated timeline

	dAIEDGE project																																						
	Year 1												Year 2												Year 3														
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36			
Open Call Preparation and Management																																							
Open Call launch, dissemination and management																																							
Evaluation and Follow up of Exchange Programme																																							
Evaluation of proposals and selection process																																							
SGA Preparation and Signature																																							
FSTP recipients follow-up & payments																																							
Evaluation and Follow up of Collaborative Projects																																							
Evaluation of proposals and selection process																																							
SGA Preparation and Signature																																							
FSTP recipients follow-up & payments																																							

12. ANNEX B

The following chart presents the deliverables of WP8 with due dates

Number	Deliverables	Lead Beneficiary	2023				2024								2025								2026																				
			Sep	Oct	Nov	Dic	Ene	Feb	Mar	Abr	May	Jun	Jul	Ago	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dic	Ene	Feb	Mar	Abr	May	Jun	Jul	Ago	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dic	Ene	Feb	Mar	Abr	May	Jun	Jul	Ago	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dic	
D8.1	dAIEDGE Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan	IOT-DIH																																									
D8.2	Call Announcement and Guide for Applicants – Call Nr 1	FBA																																									
D8.3	Open Call and FSTP Management Report	FBA																																									
D8.4	Seminars, workshop and events - Event Nr 1	IOT-DIH																																									
D8.5	Call Announcement and Guide for Applicants – Call Nr 2	FBA																																									
D8.6	Call Announcement and Guide for Applicants – Call Nr 3	FBA																																									
D8.7	Seminars, workshop and events - Event Nr 2	IOT-DIH																																									
D8.8	Seminars, workshop and events - Event Nr 3	IOT-DIH																																									
D8.9	dAIEDGE Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan – update Nr 1	IOT-DIH																																									
D8.10	dAIEDGE Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan – update Nr 2	IOT-DIH																																									

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